

Preparation, Infrared Absorption Spectra and X-Ray Powder Diffraction Patterns of Mixed (Ca + Ba + Mg) Hydroxylapatites

HIMADRI CH. PANDEY and PREMA N. PATEL*

Post-Graduate Department of Chemistry, G. M. College, Sambalpur, Orissa

and

(Mrs.) SHANTI PANDEY

Department of Zoology, Women's College, Sambalpur, Orissa

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Homogeneous solid solutions of calcium, barium and magnesium hydroxylapatite have been prepared over the entire compositional range by the method of co-precipitation in aqueous media. Frequencies (cm^{-1}) and assignments for the infrared absorption and the lattice constants of the solid solutions have been measured and found to vary linearly with composition between those of the pure and members.

CALCIUM hydroxylapatite (CaHA), $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$, the principal inorganic constituent of human bones and teeth^{1,2} belongs to an isomorphous series of compounds known as apatites. Calcium hydroxylapatite (CaHA) which exists in nature as the mineral hydroxylapatite, and is similar if not identical to bone mineral, can be prepared from aqueous media^{3,4}. The ionic radii⁵ of calcium (0.99 Å), barium (1.35 Å) and magnesium (0.65 Å) are close enough together so that it would not be surprising if solid solutions could be formed between isomorphous substances containing these ions. It undergoes a series of cationic and anionic replacement reactions⁶. $\text{Ca}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{Ba}^{2+}$ and/or Mg^{2+} replacement reactions in CaHA are of extreme biological significance. They form the basis of incorporation of Ba^{2+} and Mg^{2+} into human skeletal system according to the following equation :

Solid solutions of calcium, barium and magnesium hydroxylapatites were prepared separately earlier⁷ by firing mixtures containing various proportions of calcium, barium and magnesium hydroxylapatite at about 1300°. These samples prepared by the solid state reaction were however found to be discontinuous and non-homogeneous.

Now an attempt has been made at a new method of preparation of the homogeneous solid solutions of mixed (Ca + Ba + Mg) hydroxylapatite over the entire compositional range by the method of co-precipitation⁸⁻¹⁰.

Experimental

Materials : All chemicals used for the preparation of these samples were either AR (BDH) or E. Merck Extra Pure grade. Water used in the preparation and in washing was boiled to remove CO_2 and then used immediately.

Preparations : Stoichiometric quantities of ammonium dihydrogen phosphate (Solution A) and a solution containing Ca^{2+} , Ba^{2+} and Mg^{2+} ions in the proportion desired for the solid solutions (Solution B) were prepared separately in carbon-dioxide free doubly distilled water. The pH of these solutions were maintained above 11 by the addition of excess of liquor ammonia. Then a part of the Solution B was taken in a flask (2 L) fitted with two separating funnels and a delivery tube. Solution A and Solution B were taken separately in the separating funnels and added dropwise to the flask simultaneously. Precipitation was carried out in carbon-dioxide free atmosphere and the precipitation medium was well stirred by bubbling CO_2 free air.

The precipitate and mother liquor were aged by boiling under reflux for 30 min to improve the homogeneity and crystallinity of the precipitate and maintenance of the desired pH during precipitation was ensured by testing the filtrate after separation of the precipitate, since any alternation of pH of the medium during precipitation leads to the formation of calcium deficient apatites¹¹. The precipitate was washed thoroughly with doubly distilled water to free it from ammonium salts. Samples dried at 100°

* To whom correspondence is to be made.

for few hours were analysed colorimetrically¹² and their molar volumes were determined by density method using toluene¹³ as a solvent.

Infrared absorption techniques :

Samples used for infrared studies were acetone washed and air dried. All the bands were recorded on a Granting Infrared Spectrophotometer model 577 (Perkin-Elmer). A few milligrams of the sample was ground with two drops of Nujol in an agate mortar. About 50 mg of a fine polythylene powder (VESTOLENA 6016 Chem. Weke Huels, Germany) was added. The resulting paste was melted at about 140° and pressed between glass plates to a slightly wedge-shaped film of average thickness 0.1 mm.

X-ray diffraction techniques :

Samples dried at 110° for few hours were used for X-ray diffraction. The X-ray diffraction patterns of the samples were obtained with Siemens Powder Diffractometer with NaCl(TL) counter employing CuK_{α} (Nickel filtered) radiation with a scanning speed of 1 degree (2θ) per min (using tube voltage of 30 kV and 24 mA respectively).

Lattice constant measurements :

CaHA, BaHA and MgHA are hexagonal with two lattice constants a_0 and c_0 . These were determined^{14,15} for all the samples by measuring the diffraction angle 2θ of the three planes, (312), (213) and (321). Each sample was thoroughly mixed with 25% NaCl (recrystallized from HCl) which served as a standard. So that the observed values of $\sin \theta$ for the solid solution lines could be directly corrected for absorption and instrumental errors. The lattice constant of NaCl at 25 was taken to be 5.6403 Å. A least square calculation on the corrected values of $\sin \theta$ for the three reflections then gave the two parameters, a_0 and c_0 , for each sample. The diffraction lines were quite sharp and the diffraction angle was read by counting over the top of the peak with the scaling unit and taking the position of maximum intensity from a plot of intensity vs 2θ . The average probable error in unit cell parameters is less than ± 0.005 Å.

Results and Discussion

The results of chemical analysis of the samples were given in Table 1. Based on the fact that a mole of each sample has a total 10 g-atoms of calcium and/or barium and/or magnesium, the molecular formulae of the samples were calculated from the columns 2-4 and included in column 6 of the Table 1. The g-atom ratio $\frac{(\text{Ca} + \text{Ba} + \text{Mg})}{P}$ in a mole of each sample was calculated from the results of

columns 2-5 and given in column 8 of the table. The fact that the observed value of molar g-atom ratios of $\frac{\text{Ca}}{P}, \frac{\text{Ba}}{P}, \frac{\text{Mg}}{P}$ for the end members and

$\frac{\text{Ca} + \text{Ba} + \text{Mg}}{P}$ were found to be equal to 1.625 (theo-

retical 1.67) is consistent with the formation of homogeneous solid solution¹⁶. This was further supported by the closeness of the values of molar volumes of the end members and those of the intermediate samples which lie within the range of end members.

The formation of solid solutions can be further confirmed by the X-ray diffraction analysis. It is well established that all the members of the apatite series exhibit hexagonal-dipyramidal class-6/m (space group C_{6h}/I_2)^{17,18}. Lattice parameters showed until cell dialation and contraction consequent upon the introduction of bigger ion Ba^{2+} (1.35Å) and smaller ion Mg^{2+} (0.65 Å) respectively in place of Ca^{2+} (0.99 Å) ion in the apatite lattice. Such dialation and contraction with the proportion of Ca-Ba-MgHA was evident that the unit cell volume of the samples calculated on the basis of the experimentally determined lattice constant increased with the proportion of barium content and decreased with the proportion of magnesium content in Ca-Ba-MgHA. This, of course is the real evidence for solid solution in this series and clearly shows that these preparations are not mixtures of two components or one component with adsorbed material.

The CaHA and its solid solutions with barium and magnesium have hexagonal crystalline structures and are interesting examples of solid state of fairly simple molecules of tetrahedral symmetry where bands become allowed due to relaxation of the molecular symmetry¹⁹ selection rules due to the influence of site symmetry. The ideal symmetry of tribasic phosphate ion in the free or undistorted state in tetrahedral -- a member of Td point group. In this ideal symmetry condition only a few absorption bands corresponding to ν_4 (570 cm^{-1}) and ν_3 (1075 cm^{-1}) of PO_4^{3-} and ν_1 (630 cm^{-1}) and ν_3 (3450 cm^{-1}) of OH^- were clearly observed. From the spectra of the samples it could be seen that the ν_3 and ν_4 frequencies corresponding to PO_4^{3-} ion and ν_1 and ν_3 corresponding to OH^- ion are shifted to lower frequencies and the shape of the peaks was being effected by the introduction of barium and magnesium ion into the samples. The shift of the ν_3 and ν_4 of PO_4^{3-} vibrations to lower frequencies may be due to the effect of binding energy and atomic mass. The lowering of frequency of ν_3 of OH^- indicates the presence of hydroxyl group in the apatite²⁰. This hydroxyl group in hydroxylapatite lie in the internuclear axis coincident with

TABLE 1—CHEMICAL ANALYSES OF CALCIUM, BARIUM AND MAGNESIUM HYDROXYLAPATITE AND THEIR SOLID SOLUTIONS

Sample No.	Wt%		Mol. Vol.	Molecular Formulae	G. atom ratio	Lattice Parameter		Unit cell volume	Frequency (cm ⁻¹)			
	Ca	Ba				Mg	P		a	c	PO ₄ ³⁻ (ν ₄)	PO ₄ ³⁻ (ν ₃)
1.	39.88	—	—	18.15	Ca ₁₀ (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.665	9.37	6.86	593.12	570sh	1075br	3450sh
2.	29.64	9.77	8.34	17.63	Ca _{7.8} Ba _{0.78} Mg _{1.43} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.666	9.43	6.90	531.38	560sh	1065br	3448sh
3.	25.93	13.97	4.27	17.19	Ca ₇ Ba _{1.1} Mg _{1.9} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.666						
4.	25.28	19.35	2.56	16.29	Ca _{7.3} Ba _{1.6} Mg _{1.3} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.666						
5.	20.99	21.59	4.67	16.24	Ca ₆ Ba _{1.9} Mg _{2.3} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.656	9.52	6.96	546.28	552sh	1060br	3430sh
6.	18.15	22.34	6.41	16.35	Ca _{5.13} Ba _{1.93} Mg ₃ (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.646						
7.	16.20	30.54	4.42	15.04	Ca _{3.0} Ba _{2.75} Mg _{3.25} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.665						
8.	13.02	33.74	5.39	14.74	Ca _{4.1} Ba _{2.1} Mg _{2.9} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.667	9.56	7.00	554.01	550sh	1055br	3420sh
9.	10.24	35.11	9.77	16.98	Ca _{3.9} Ba _{2.9} Mg _{4.4} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.652						
10.	9.19	39.75	5.67	13.98	Ca _{3.03} Ba _{3.93} Mg _{5.11} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.656						
11.	6.13	39.89	7.81	14.22	Ca ₂ Ba _{4.9} Mg _{4.3} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.654	9.62	7.12	570.64	548sh	1055br	3400sh
12.	3.93	41.05	9.41	14.26	Ca _{1.03} Ba _{5.93} Mg _{5.03} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.666						
13.	2.96	49.03	6.74	12.89	Ca _{0.93} Ba _{6.13} Mg ₄ (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.665						
14.	—	45.59	9.87	13.72	Ba _{4.9} Mg _{5.1} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.666	9.72	7.94	592.38	545sh	1052br	3385sh
15.	69.46	—	—	9.41	Ba ₁₀ (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.664	10.19	7.70	692.42	542sh	1048br	3355sh
16.	—	—	18.51	21.96	Mg ₁₀ (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.665	8.72	6.42	422.77	530sh	1025br	3375sh

br = broad ; sh = sharp.

six fold screw axis. In Barnes expression²¹

$$\nu = \frac{1}{2\pi C} \sqrt{\frac{K}{\mu}}$$

which gives a relationship between frequency, atomic mass and force constant. The vibrational frequencies are dependent on the reduction mass μ of the participating atoms and restoring forces K between atoms, all other terms remaining constant. When the equilibrium distance between the positive and the negative atoms of the molecule is decreased K generally increases in the above equation. This equilibrium distance depends on the ionic radii of the participating atoms in the molecule. Substitution of Ca^{2+} with a nucleus like Ba^{2+} and/or Mg^{2+} gives rise to stronger co-ordination of the PO_4^{3-} group through oxygen. This in turn weakens the P-O bond, lowering K (increasing P-O bond length) and the frequency is lowered. The PO_4^{3-} bonding is normally around 520 cm^{-1} and bending modes do not shift very much under these conditions. But here the substitution is more complex, presumably because of the splitting of the triply degenerate mode at 600 cm^{-1} and thus there is an increase in the frequency from 520 cm^{-1} to 570 cm^{-1} . This theoretical explanation agrees well with the experimental data.

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